

Rethink : Theories on the origin of life ?

Monica Cai

BASIS International School Shenzhen

Xiyan.Cai10943-bisz@basischina.com

1. Preface

I came to this world perceiving what was around me: the hospital, my bedroom, the sunshine, and school. I grew day by day, taking in baby food, then child food, then adult food, absorbing them, then excreting them. I ran in the sun, panted and sweated, and Mom gave me a smile and gently wiped my forehead with a napkin. As I went on to middle school, I learned about the characteristics of life, and they molded my first thoughts on how we define life.

2. What is 'being alive' ?

Being alive means being able to respond to both internal and external needs and interactions. Today, we commonly describe all lifeforms as organisms. Organisms could be described as beings that possess certain traits. These traits include reproduction, growth and development, cellular structures and composition, the ability to intake and harness energy, the ability to maintain a stable internal environment (homeostasis), the overall ability of a species to pass down genetic information (and the traits they code for), and response to both external and internal stimuli. Possessing all these traits, beings are seen as "alive". We respond to our internal feelings of hunger by taking in food from external sources. We strive to maintain homeostasis and equilibrium while taking on those changes from the external environment that push us to adapt to them. We respond to one another, to other living organisms, and to the abiotic surroundings, such as shading ourselves from the sun or jumping into muddy puddles (or avoiding them as we get older). Being alive is being able to respond.

The Cell Theory states that "every living thing is made of cells, and everything a living thing does is done by the cells that make it up" (Cudmore 1978). Unicellular organisms, although smaller in size, possess a similar organizational structure. These organisms are composed of a single cell, but within it, they contain different subcellular structures (organelles) that each complete different functions needed for cell survival. These organelles also have internal structures, such as thylakoids in chloroplasts in certain photoautotrophs. Cells of similar functions in multicellular organisms form a tissue to collectively accomplish a certain task,

and two or more types of tissues form an organ to collectively accomplish an overall task. Organ systems consisting of several organs then make up a complete multicellular organism.

On a molecular level, it is now recognized that in both unicellular and multicellular organisms, genes (or DNA sequences) are the blueprint for building and sustaining each organism. These blueprints are then passed down from parent cell to daughter cell, from one generation to the next. In the cell cycle, the synthesis phase is responsible for DNA replication by transcription and translation, with these genetic instructions then carried out in the organism by proteins. Proteins are assembled through a series of stages. In its primary structure, the protein is simply a chain of amino acids linked by peptide bonds. In a protein's secondary structure, it either coils into an alpha helix or forms a beta-pleated sheet (note: there are many other structures as well, but these two are the most common) where points in the amino acid strand are linked by hydrogen bonds. In the tertiary structure, the R groups of individual amino acids interact (some are hydrophobic and others are hydrophilic; some are charged and others are uncharged) and form intermolecular bonds (e.g. disulfide bridges). Then finally, in the quaternary structure, multiple tertiary structure polypeptides are assembled together to form a final protein, held by interactions similar to those in the tertiary structure.

3. Virus the exception

Yet, one common exception known to our curriculum is viruses. Viruses, much like living organisms, have protein compositions. Viruses have a protein capsid enclosing their genetic material, serving as a protective barrier that allows the virus genome to be delivered into the interior of a host cell. Viruses do not pass as actual organisms, since they do not possess the many traits that would've tagged them as "living." For example, viruses cannot reproduce without a host (which means that they are dependent upon the presence of another organism for reproduction), and they also do not grow in size or develop in complexity. So, do viruses count as a kind of life form? Despite attaining many features that link viruses to live organisms, in my opinion, they are not a form of life because they lack certain distinct char-

acteristics that distinguish life as of greater capabilities.

4. The theories on the origin of life

The discussion on whether viruses are a form of life brought me to another question - how had life originated? Multiple theories have been suggested to explain the origins of life. Initially, religious and cultural sects believed that all organisms were created by a divine being. Then people progressed to believe in abiogenesis, where the non-living bore life, which explains to them why mold, being alive, would “grow” from bread. With “science,” people prefer the extraterrestrial theory where life was first introduced to Earth in the form of spores from outer space and reproduced to create all the life forms. In the modern day, most people prefer the Chemical Evolution Theory, where life is believed to originate from single monomers combined to form polymers, which are then enclosed by membranes to acquire cellular properties and functions.

In a theorized former world of RNA domination, RNA accounted for information storage, self-replication, and enzymatic functions (Bernhardt, 2012). This was a much-needed role that neither DNA nor proteins could take over. However, was RNA in fact capable of all those roles and responsibilities? Many questioned how such a complex molecule could have arisen prebiotically, how only certain long sequences of RNA would be able to perform catalysis, and how they were inherently unstable. Some proposed, defended their capabilities, and others denied them. Yet their true potential remains disclosed, existing in the past, in history, rather than how scientists today define them.

5. Theories vs theorems

When I was young, I took a class on Greek mythology, and it was agreed that one of the main purposes of people creating and passing down these mythologies is to explain nature and the mysteries people encounter. Ancient people used mythologies to explain what they could not otherwise. Similarly, I think theories are used to dictate what has not yet been explained, yet it is often a subjective supposition based on one’s own encounters and findings. Many are already logically supported when first raised in public, and some are proven over long years after publication. Theories are constructed for two reasons: to explain what has not been explained and what doesn’t make sense, and to form a global consensus on a particular subject matter. Theories do not include facts, which are things proven or (often widely) known to be true. Whereas theories are simply suppositions based on patterns and cannot be demonstrated through statements (Google exemplifies Einstein’s theory of relativity), theorems are suppositions that can be demonstrated (*e.g.* Pythagorean Theorem).

6. Ending remark

For me, it seems at least for now, it is out of my capacity to determine which theory on the origin of life is more reasonable and how exactly life should be defined. But I realized that there might not exist a sole definition to these topics that involve more than scientific findings: in these logical, rational scientific explanations of the world, there also overlooks a deeper level of philosophical thinking of the uncertainty and the unknown.